

CORRELATION BETWEEN SPIRITUAL AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT :-

Emotional Intelligence can be defined as the ability in a person to identify, assess and control the emotions of oneself, others or and of a group. While the Spiritual intelligence is the ultimate intelligence which we address & solve problems of meaning & value , the intelligence with which we can place our actions & our lives in wider, riche , meaning – giving context , the intelligence with which we can assess that one course of action or one life path is more meaningful than another. The investigator was interested in studying to find out the Correlation between Emotional Intelligence & Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school teachers of Gangamata Madhyamik Vidyalaya , Verkhede , Tal.& Dist.Dhule in Maharashtra.The investigator used the tools for present study were 1) –Emotional Intelligence Test constructed by N.K.Chaddha ,2)– Roqan Spiritual Intelligence Test constructed by Roquiya Zainuddin & Ms. Anjum Ahmed. . It is revealed through the study that the male & female secondary school teachers have significant correlation in their Emotional Intelligence & Spiritual Intelligence. The main findings of the study are, Spiritual Intelligence & Emotional Intelligence does not correlates significantly among secondary school teachers.

INTRODUCTION :- In 21st century, the modern society is characterized by a lack of emotional & spiritual intelligence as most of us worship materialism & instant emotional & physical gratification. Consequently the society turn to food , drink, drugs, gambling or sex to try to fill ourselves up & to get rid of the emptiness that they feel. there tends to be a lack of morals , a lack of family ,a lack of sense of community ,& ultimately a lack of inner peace & meaning in the lives. The importance of emotional as well as spiritual intelligence is obvious as it gives direction to our life in critical moments.

Emotional Intelligence can be defined as the ability in a person to identify, assess and control the emotions of oneself, others or and of a group. Goleman (1995,1998) defined Emotional

Intelligence as “the composite set of capabilities that enable a person to manage himself/herself and others”. How smartly a person can understand his/her emotions and controls these emotions in any given situation can be termed as emotional intelligence.

According to Zohar & Marshal , 1999, “ Spiritual intelligence is the ultimate intelligence which we address & solve problems of meaning & value , the intelligence with which we can place our actions & our lives in wider , richer , meaning – giving context , the intelligence with which we can assess that one course of action or one life path is more meaningful than another.” Spiritual intelligence is something that is apart from organized religion & contains some or all the components as – alignment with ones values & ideals , perceive connections to the greater whole , recognize & use all parts of the self , use trans-logical thinking , & explore inner realms.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM :- The investigator was interested in studying to find out the Correlation between Emotional Intelligence & Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school teachers of Gangamata Madhyamik Vidyalaya , Verkhede , Tal.& Dist.Dhule in Maharashtra. Hence, the present study has been captioned as , “A Correlational Study of Emotional & Spiritual Intelligence of Secondary School Teachers .”

SCOPE & LIMITATIONS :- The present study has been limited only for the secondary school teachers of Gangamata Madhyamik Vidyalaya , Verkhede , Tal. & Dist. Dhule in Maharashtra State.

NEED & IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY :- In the stressful environment , there is necessary to inculcate the moral , emotional & spiritual values in personal for getting better adjustment and status in the society. Also for getting inner peace, satisfaction & also for social peace. To live such a beautiful life gifted from the God , the spiritual foundation is very must. To go near to the God , to get self-realization , self-actualization each & every person should have the spiritual values. Similarly to see the divine value in school-children , every teacher should have spiritual basics.

School is the miniature unit of society. Various types of human factors working in the school. In which Management and Director body, Administration, Head master of the School, Teachers, Non-teaching staff etc. Besides all these factors a very important factor that is the Students similarly their parents also. Daily the teacher interacts with all these factors more or less. For that the teacher should be healthy mentally as well as emotionally. So the Emotional intelligence of the teacher should be at higher level. So the present study needed for inculcating the Emotional & Spiritual Intelligence Scores of the Secondary School Teachers. Also the researcher found out that how the emotional & spiritual intelligence correlates .

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :-

- 1) To obtain the Emotional Intelligence scores of secondary school teachers.
- 2) To obtain the Spiritual Intelligence scores of secondary school teachers.
- 3) To correlate the Emotional & Spiritual Intelligence of male secondary school teachers.
- 4) To correlate the Emotional & Spiritual Intelligence of female secondary school teachers.
- 5) To correlate the Emotional & Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school teachers.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY :-

- 1) There is no significant correlation between Spiritual Intelligence & Emotional Intelligence of male secondary school teachers.
- 2) There is no significant correlation between Spiritual Intelligence & Emotional Intelligence of female secondary school teachers.
- 3) There is no significant correlation between Spiritual Intelligence & Emotional Intelligence of secondary school teachers.

METHODOLOGY :- The investigator used the survey method for the present study.

SAMPLE :- The sample taken for the present study by the investigator are 10 female & 10 male secondary school teachers.

RESEARCH TOOL :- In the present study , for the data collection, the standardized tests

- 1) Emotional Intelligence Test constructed by N.K.Chaddha
- 2) Roqan Spiritual Intelligence Test constructed by Roquiya Zainuddin & Ms. Anjum Ahmed. The test contains 6 dimensions as – The inner self, The inter-self, Biostoria, Life perspectives, Spiritual actualization , & Value orientation. All includes 78 items. the reliability of the test is 0.73 calculated by Crenbach's Alpha coefficient, & 0.70 computed by Guttman's Split- Half coefficient method. that is very high reliability. Validity of the test is so high, which is 0.85.

* **ANALYSIS OF THE DATA :-** The Spearman's correlation coefficient values of Spiritual intelligence & Emotional intelligence among male, female & total secondary school teachers are shown in the following table;

Sample	N	p	Significance level (0.05)
Male secondary school teachers	10	0.38	Not Significant
Female secondary school teachers	10	0.05	Not Significant
Total secondary school teachers	20	0.17	Not Significant

INTERPRETATION :- From the above table , it is evident that in case of male, female & total secondary school teachers the calculated **p**-values are very low, so the null hypotheses made for the secondary school teachers were somewhat accepted.

FINDINGS :-

- 1) There is fair correlation between Spiritual Intelligence & Emotional Intelligence of male secondary school teachers as the correlation coefficient value is 0.38.
- 2) There is very low means negligible correlation between Spiritual Intelligence & Emotional Intelligence of female secondary school teachers as the correlation coefficient value is 0.05.
- 3) There is less correlation between Spiritual Intelligence & Emotional Intelligence of total male & female secondary school teachers as the correlation coefficient value is 0.17.

CONCLUSION :- The Spiritual Intelligence & Emotional Intelligence does not correlates significantly among male as well as female secondary school teachers. So here the investigator conclude that spirituality & emotionality both are the different & both have the separate identities & qualities, hence they does not highly correlate with each other.

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